

MASTER TEACHERS' TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE PRACTICES, WELL-BEING, CHALLENGES, AND PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges, and performance of Master Teachers in public secondary schools within the Division of Bohol for School Year 2025–2026. Using a descriptive–correlational quantitative design, the study determined the participants' profiles and explored the relationships between demographic variables and key outcomes, and examined the interconnections among technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges, and performance. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, weighted mean, Chi-square test, t-test, ANOVA, and Pearson correlation. The findings revealed that Master Teachers consistently provided a high level of technical assistance, particularly in conducting classroom observations and offering feedback. Mentoring and coaching, however, were often implemented informally. Their well-being was also rated high across physical, emotional, social, and professional domains. Despite this, they encountered moderate to high challenges, with time pressures and workload demands emerging as the most pressing concern. Even with these constraints, their performance remained very satisfactory, as reflected in the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) results. Further analysis indicated that certain profile variables significantly shaped the key outcomes, while no direct associations were observed among technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges, and performance. These results emphasize the need to address workload and clarify roles to sustain instructional leadership. While Master Teachers continue to demonstrate strong leadership capacity, the persistence of workload intensity and role ambiguity poses barriers. It calls for targeted interventions, including structured mentoring programs, workload management, and role clarification, were recommended to strengthen both performance and overall well-being.

Keywords: *Technical Assistance Practices, Master Teachers, Teacher Well-Being, Instructional Leadership, and Workload Challenges*

INTRODUCTION

Master Teachers play a critical role in strengthening instructional quality through the provision of technical assistance, mentoring, and leadership support in schools. As articulated in DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, they are expected to guide teachers' professional growth and ensure the consistent implementation of standards aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). However, when mentoring functions are carried out as compliance-driven tasks without structured systems, clear role expectations, and sustained support, their impact on instructional improvement becomes limited.

Globally, mentoring systems continue to face gaps in implementation, with evidence showing that only a portion of teachers receive sustained professional guidance. Although Master Teachers are recognized as instructional leaders, a significant number lack formal preparation in mentoring and coaching (Laureano & Manalang, 2023). This disconnect between policy expectations and actual capacity constrains the effectiveness of technical assistance. At the division level, studies in Bohol have shown that while Master Teachers demonstrate moderate to high levels of instructional support, their effectiveness is affected by inconsistent mentoring practices, limited access to professional development, and increasing workload demands (Arombo, 2023). Such conditions contribute to role ambiguity and uneven implementation of instructional support.

Instructional leadership, therefore, operates within a complex system where technical assistance practices, well-being, professional challenges, and performance interact. Master Teachers are expected to perform multiple roles—as mentors, evaluators, coordinators, and instructional leaders—while maintaining high levels of performance as reflected in their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). However, existing research often examines these variables independently, providing limited understanding of how they function collectively in shaping instructional leadership outcomes.

This study addresses this gap by examining Master Teachers' technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges, and performance within a unified framework. It aims to determine how these variables interact and influence instructional leadership effectiveness in public secondary schools in the Division of Bohol. Furthermore, the study proposes a Professional Development Program grounded in the findings to enhance mentoring competencies, clarify roles, and support the overall well-being of Master Teachers.

The study is anchored on several theoretical perspectives. Instructional Leadership Theory (Hallinger & Murphy, 1985) explains how leadership practices such

as mentoring, supervision, and feedback improve teaching and learning outcomes. Leader–Member Exchange Theory (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995) emphasizes the importance of professional relationships in shaping mentoring effectiveness and well-being. The Job Demands–Resources Theory (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007) provides a framework for understanding how workload and institutional support influence well-being and performance. Role Theory (Kahn et al., 1964) highlights the effects of role ambiguity and overload on professional functioning, while Goal Setting Theory (Locke & Latham, 1990) explains how structured guidance and feedback contribute to improved performance outcomes. Together, these theories explain how technical assistance, professional relationships, job demands, and institutional conditions shape the effectiveness of Master Teachers.

The study is further supported by key policy frameworks that define and regulate instructional leadership in Philippine basic education. Republic Act No. 9155 establishes shared accountability and decentralized leadership, extending instructional responsibilities to Master Teachers. The PPST framework (DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017) formalizes their role in mentoring and professional development. Republic Act No. 4670 emphasizes the importance of teacher welfare, while DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015 institutionalizes performance evaluation through the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). Recent reforms under the MATATAG agenda (DepEd Order No. 16, s. 2024) further reinforce mentoring as a structured responsibility. These policies collectively underscore the need to examine how instructional leadership is enacted in practice.

Empirical studies also highlight that demographic and professional characteristics—such as age, educational attainment, teaching load, and training—shape mentoring capacity and leadership effectiveness. At the same time, well-being influences teachers’ ability to sustain instructional roles, while challenges such as workload, resource limitations, and unclear role expectations may hinder performance. Existing evidence further shows that technical assistance practices contribute to improved instructional outcomes, while well-being and professional challenges significantly affect performance.

Despite these findings, limited research has examined how these variables operate as an interconnected system. This study, therefore, provides a more comprehensive understanding of instructional leadership by analyzing the relationships among technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges, and performance. By doing so, it contributes to the development of context-based interventions that strengthen instructional leadership and improve school performance outcomes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of technical assistance practices provided by Master Teachers, their level of well-being, the challenges they encounter in their instructional leadership roles, and their performance based on the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings for School Year 2024–2025 in public secondary schools within the Division of Bohol for School Year 2025–2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Master Teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 educational attainment;
 - 1.4 ancillary tasks/ designations.
 - 1.5 length of service as a Master Teacher;
 - 1.6 number of teachers mentored or supervised;
 - 1.7 teaching load; and
 - 1.8 trainings/ seminars attended?
2. What is the level of Master Teachers' technical assistance practices, as perceived by the Master Teachers and the teachers they mentor, in terms of:
 - 2.1 mentoring and coaching;
 - 2.2 classroom observation and feedback;
 - 2.3 facilitation of Learning Action Cells (LACs) and peer learning; and
 - 2.4. monitoring and evaluation of teacher performance?
3. What is the level of well-being of Master Teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. physical well-being;
 - 3.2. emotional well-being;
 - 3.3. social well-being; and
 - 3.4. professional well-being?
4. What is the level of challenges encountered by the Master Teachers in providing technical assistance in terms of:
 - 4.1. time and workload constraints;
 - 4.2. availability of resources and support;
 - 4.3. clarity of roles and expectations; and
 - 4.4. capacity-building or training opportunities?
5. What is the level of Master Teachers' performance based on the IPCRF for the School Year 2024-2025?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the participants' demographic profile in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, ancillary tasks/ designations length of service as a Master Teacher, number of teachers mentored, teaching load, and relevant training/ seminars attended, and their:
 - 6.1. technical assistance practices,
 - 6.2. well-being,
 - 6.3. challenges encountered, and
 - 6.4. performance?
7. Is there a significant relationship among the following variables of the Master Teachers:
 - 7.1. technical assistance practices and well-being;
 - 7.2. technical assistance practices and challenges encountered;
 - 7.3. technical assistance practices and performance;
 - 7.4. challenges encountered and well-being;
 - 7.5. challenges encountered and performance; and
 - 7.6. well-being and performance?

8. Based on the findings, what Professional Development Program can be proposed for Master Teachers?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive–correlational quantitative design with comparative features. It described the demographic profile of Master Teachers and assessed their levels of technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges, and performance. It also examined the relationships among these variables and identified differences across selected groups based on gender and educational attainment. This design was appropriate as it allowed the analysis of variables in their natural setting without manipulation, providing a basis for identifying patterns and relationships. The results served as input for the development of a Professional Development Program aimed at strengthening technical assistance and instructional leadership among Master Teachers.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the Department of Education (DepEd) Division of Bohol, located in the Central Visayas Region. The division spans three congressional districts and includes 56 school districts across 47 municipalities and one city. It comprises public secondary schools with varying sizes, geographic locations, and resource conditions. This diverse educational setting provided an appropriate context for examining the implementation of technical assistance practices and instructional leadership among Master Teachers, reflecting variations in school environments within the division.

Research Participants

The study utilized stratified random sampling to ensure representation across the three congressional districts, school levels (Junior and Senior High School), and municipalities within the Division of Bohol. The primary participants were Master Teachers actively engaged in mentoring, coaching, classroom observation, and instructional support. To provide complementary perspectives and minimize bias, two recipient-teachers were selected for each Master Teacher. From a total population of 275 Master Teachers, a sample of 163 Master Teachers was determined using Slovin's formula at a 5% margin of error. This was paired with 326 recipient-teachers, resulting in a total of 489 respondents. The distribution of participants was proportionally allocated across the three districts, ensuring balanced representation of mentors and mentees. This sampling approach provided a comprehensive basis for analyzing technical assistance practices and developing a Professional Development Program.

Distribution of Participants

District	No. of Towns	MT Population (N _h)	Allocated MTs (n _h)	Recipient-Teachers (2 per MT)	Total Respondents
1st	15	68	40	80	120
2nd	13	114	68	136	204
3rd	19	93	55	110	168
Total	47	275	163	326	489

Research Instrument

Data were collected using a researcher-modified survey questionnaire adapted from validated instruments and relevant frameworks. The tool consisted of six parts. The first part described the demographic profile of Master Teachers, including age, gender, educational attainment, ancillary tasks, length of service, number of teachers mentored, teaching load, and trainings attended. The second part measured technical assistance practices across mentoring and coaching, classroom observation and feedback, facilitation of Learning Action Cells (LACs), and monitoring and evaluation. It used a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (Never) to 5 (Always). The third part assessed well-being in terms of physical, emotional, social, and professional dimensions using a 5-point agreement scale. The fourth part examined challenges encountered, covering workload, resources and support, role clarity, and capacity-building, also using a 5-point frequency scale. The fifth part measured performance using respondents' latest IPCRF ratings (SY 2024–2025) based on DepEd standards. The final part gathered open-ended responses on improving technical assistance. The instrument underwent pilot testing with 30 Master Teachers and 60 teachers. Reliability was established using Cronbach's alpha (≥ 0.70), and necessary revisions were made prior to final administration.

Research Procedure

A formal request was submitted to the University President and Campus Director through the Dean of the School of Advanced Studies and endorsed to the Schools Division Office of DepEd Bohol. Upon approval, authorization was secured from the Schools Division Superintendent and coordinated with district supervisors and school heads. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. The purpose of the study, confidentiality of responses, and voluntary nature of participation were clearly explained. Data were collected using both printed and online questionnaires (Google Forms) to ensure accessibility. Printed copies were distributed to schools with limited internet access, while digital links were shared through official communication channels. Participants were given 5–7 days to complete the instrument. All retrieved data were consolidated, verified, and encoded for analysis. Responses were stored in password-protected files accessible only to the researcher, and ethical standards were strictly observed throughout the process.

Data Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to analyze the data. Frequency and percentage were used to describe the demographic profile of Master Teachers. The weighted mean was utilized to determine the levels of technical assistance practices, well-being, and challenges encountered. Responses for technical assistance, well-being, and challenges were measured using a 5-point Likert scale, while performance was assessed using the IPCRF rating scale (SY 2024–2025) based on DepEd standards. To determine relationships between demographic variables and key outcomes, the Chi-square test of independence was applied. Differences across groups were analyzed using t-test and ANOVA, where appropriate. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (r) was used to examine the relationships among technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges, and performance. All statistical analyses were conducted using Jamovi version 2.6.44.

Level of Master Teachers' Technical Assistance Practices

Scale	Range	Categorical Response	Interpretation
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Very High Extent of Technical Assistance Practices
4	3.50– 4.49	Often	High Extent of Technical Assistance Practices
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderate Extent of Technical Assistance Practices
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely	Low Extent of Technical Assistance Practices
1	below 1.49	Never	Very Low Extent of Technical Assistance Practices

Level of Master Teachers' Well-Being

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.50–5.00	Strongly Agree	Outstanding – Teachers consistently sustain health, resilience, collegiality, and professional satisfaction at the highest level.
4	3.50–4.49	Agree	Excellent – Teachers regularly sustain well-being across physical, emotional, social, and professional dimensions.
3	2.50–3.49	Neutral	Good – Teachers moderately sustain well-being; they manage demands but with occasional inconsistencies.
2	1.50–2.49	Disagree	Weak – Teachers encounter difficulties; stress and role demands often affect their effectiveness.
1	1.00–1.49	Strongly Disagree	Poor – Teachers struggle significantly with health, resilience, relationships, and professional fulfillment.

Level of Master Teachers' Challenges Encountered in Providing Technical Assistance

Scale	Range	Categorical Response	Interpretation
5	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Very High Extent of Challenges Experienced
4	3.50 – 4.49	Often	High Extent of Challenges Experienced
3	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderate Extent of Challenges Experienced
2	1.50 – 2.49	Rarely	Low Extent of Challenges Experienced
1	below 1.49	Never	Very Low or No Challenges Experienced

Level of Master Teachers' Performance (Based on IPCRF SY 2024- 2025)

Scale	Range	Categorical Response	Interpretation
5	4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding	Excellent Performance
4	3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory	Above Average Performance
3	2.500 – 3.499	Satisfactory	Average Performance
2	1.500 – 2.499	Unsatisfactory	Below Average Performance
1	below 1.499	Poor	Needs Improvement

RESULTS

This section presents the results of the study, including the analysis and interpretation of data on Master Teachers' technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges encountered, and performance based on IPCRF ratings for SY 2024–2025 in the Division of Bohol. The first part describes the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, ancillary designations, length of service as Master Teacher, number of teachers mentored, teaching load, and relevant trainings attended. Data were analyzed using frequency and percentage distributions to provide a clear and systematic presentation of respondent characteristics. These variables serve as the basis for contextualizing and interpreting the subsequent findings of the study.

**Table 1
PARTICIPANTS' PROFILE (MASTER TEACHERS)
n = 163**

	(F)	(P)	Rank
1.1 Age (in years)			
45–49	48	29.4	1
50–54	31	19.0	2
40–44	27	16.6	3
55–59	25	15.3	4
35–39	13	8.0	5
30–34	11	6.7	6
60-65	8	4.9	7
1.2 Gender			
Female	141	86.5	1
Male	22	13.4	2
1.3 Educational Attainment			
CAR MA (Completed Academic Req.)	51	31.3	1
MA Graduate with Doctoral Units	41	25.2	2

1.4 Ancillary Tasks/ designation			
Subject Area Coordinator	141	85.98	1
LAC Leader	114	69.51	2
Committee Chair	72	43.90	3
Department Head	45	27.44	4
School In Charge/ OIC	22	13.41	5
Class Advisers	7	4.27	7
School Paper / Publication Adviser	5	3.05	8
Guidance Designate / Counselor	4	2.44	9
Other Specialized Ancillary Roles	8	4.88	6
1.5 Length of Service as Master Teacher			
0–3 years	85	52.15	1
4–7 years	40	24.54	2
8-11 years	15	9.20	3
15- 18 years	9	5.52	4.5
19 years and above	9	5.52	4.5
12-14 years	5	3.07	6
1.6. Number of teachers Mentored/ Supervised	(F)	(P)	Rank
1-5	85	52.1	1
6-10	35	21.5	2
11-15	18	11.0	3
16-20	15	9.2	4
21-25 or more	10	6.1	5
1.7. Teaching Load Range (Hours/week)			
0-5	18	10.9	4
6-10	27	16.6	2
11-15	3	1.8	6
16-20	13	8.0	5
21-25	20	12.3	3
26-30	82	50.3	1
1.8 Relevant Trainings/Seminars Attended			
In Service Training	163	100	1
Curriculum and instruction	150	91.46	2
LAC Session Training	91	55.49	3.5
Instructional Strategies	91	55.49	3.5
Guidelines on the Conduct of INSET(SY 2025-2026)	68	41.46	5
Assessment and Evaluation for Teachers	58	35.37	6
Instructional Supervision	56	34.15	7
PPST Coaching/Mentoring	52	31.71	8
HRMIS Orientation	40	24.39	9
Mental Health and Psychosocial Interventions	34	20.73	10
RPMS/PPST Workshops	26	15.85	11
Total	163		

Table 1 presents the profile of the 163 Master Teachers in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, ancillary tasks or designations, length of service as Master Teacher, number of teachers mentored or supervised, teaching load, and relevant trainings attended.

In terms of age, the largest group was 45–49 years old (29.4%), followed by 50–54 years (19.0%) and 40–44 years (16.6%). This indicates that most respondents are in the mid- to late-career stage, suggesting a mature pool of instructional leaders with substantial professional experience. At the same time, the smaller proportion in the younger and near-retirement age brackets implies the need for continuity planning in leadership preparation.

As to gender, the respondents were predominantly female (86.5%), while only 13.4% were male. This shows that instructional leadership roles among Master Teachers in the Division of Bohol are largely carried by women, reflecting the strong representation of female educators in school-based leadership positions.

Regarding educational attainment, the data show a highly qualified group of respondents. The largest proportion had completed academic requirements for a master's degree (31.3%), followed by those with master's degrees with doctoral units (25.2%), doctorate graduates (22.6%), and master's degree graduates (21.5%). This profile suggests that Master Teachers in the division generally possess strong academic preparation, which may support their mentoring, supervisory, and instructional leadership functions.

In terms of ancillary tasks or designations, most respondents served as Subject Area Coordinators (85.98%), followed by LAC Leaders (69.51%) and Committee Chairs (43.90%). A considerable number also held positions such as Department Head (27.44%) and School-In-Charge or Officer-in-Charge (13.41%). These results indicate that Master Teachers perform multiple instructional and administrative responsibilities beyond classroom teaching, highlighting their expanded leadership role in school operations.

For length of service as Master Teacher, the majority had served for 0–3 years (52.15%), followed by 4–7 years (24.54%). This suggests that many respondents are relatively new in the position, indicating recent expansion or appointment of Master Teachers in the division. While this may bring fresh perspectives and energy, it also points to the need for sustained support and professional development to strengthen mentoring competence and leadership stability.

As to the number of teachers mentored or supervised, most respondents handled 1–5 teachers (52.1%), followed by 6–10 teachers (21.5%). This suggests that mentoring assignments are generally manageable and may allow closer supervision and more individualized technical assistance, although a smaller group still handles larger mentoring loads.

In terms of teaching load, more than half of the respondents carried 26–30 hours per week (50.3%), followed by 6–10 hours (16.6%) and 21–25 hours (12.3%). This indicates that many Master Teachers continue to carry heavy classroom responsibilities despite their mentoring and leadership roles. Such a condition may limit the time and energy available for sustained technical assistance and instructional support.

Regarding relevant trainings and seminars attended, all respondents reported participation in In-Service Training (100.0%), and a large majority attended training in curriculum and instruction (91.46%). However, fewer had training in LAC session facilitation and instructional strategies (55.49% each), instructional supervision (34.15%), PPST coaching or mentoring (31.71%), and RPMS/PPST workshops (15.85%). This pattern suggests that while training exposure is broad, participation is stronger in general instructional areas than in specialized mentoring, supervision, and performance-management areas directly related to the Master Teacher role.

Overall, the profile shows that the respondents are predominantly female, academically prepared, and mostly mid-career professionals who perform multiple leadership assignments while carrying substantial teaching loads. The findings further suggest that although many Master Teachers are already positioned to provide instructional support, the combination of heavy workload, multiple ancillary roles, and uneven access to specialized training may affect the depth and sustainability of their technical assistance functions. This interpretation is supported by Gu et al. (2025), who emphasized that teacher mentors are more effectively sustained when institutions provide coherent professional learning opportunities and manageable workloads, and by Tarraya (2024), who found that excessive workload in Philippine public schools significantly affects teachers' effectiveness and underscores the need for stronger support systems and better task allocation.

Table 2
LEVEL OF MASTER TEACHERS' TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE PRACTICES AS PERCEIVED BY MASTER TEACHERS (MENTORS) AND TEACHERS (MENTEES)
n=489

2.1 Mentoring and Coaching	<i>As a master teacher, I...</i>	Mean	INT	RANK
1.	offer feedback and guidance after classroom visits	4.09	HE	1
2.	help teachers set instructional goals and reflect on progress through mentoring	4.02	HE	2
3.	provide coaching based on observed classroom practices	4.00	HE	3
4.	use coaching models (e.g., GROW, CLEAR) to guide conversations	3.95	HE	4
5.	conduct one-on-one mentoring sessions with teachers	3.83	HE	5
Composite Mean		3.98	HE	
2.2 Classroom Observation and Feedback	<i>As a master teacher, I...</i>	4.20	HE	
1.	focus on observable teaching practices during classroom observations	4.29	HE	1
2.	conduct pre-observation conferences to clarify the lesson objectives and expectations	4.27	HE	2
3.	conduct classroom observations using RPMS tools	4.23	HE	3
4.	use classroom observation data to guide follow-up mentoring or coaching	4.23	HE	3

5. involve teachers in reflective discussions during post-observation conferences	4.20	HE	5
6. analyze observation data to identify strengths and areas for improvement aligned with PPST indicators	4.18	HE	6
7. document observation results and share them with teachers	4.12	HE	7
8. provide timely, constructive feedback after observations.	4.11	HE	8
2.3 Facilitation of Learning Action Cells (LACs) and Peer Learning <i>As a master teacher, I...</i>	4.20	HE	
1. document LAC outputs and submit reports to school leadership	4.03	HE	1
2. align LAC topics with school improvement goals	4.03	HE	2
3. encourage peer sharing of best practices during LACs	4.00	HE	3
4. organize and facilitate LAC sessions	3.97	HE	4
5. help teachers identify learning needs for LAC planning	3.93	HE	5
2.4. Monitoring and Evaluation of Teachers' Performance <i>As a master teacher, I...</i>	4.20	HE	
1. use RPMS tools to monitor teacher performance.	4.29	HE	1
2. coordinate with school heads on performance evaluation.	4.26	HE	2
3. help teachers reflect on their performance and identify areas for professional growth.	4.21	HE	3
4. assist teachers in completing their IPCRF.	4.16	HE	4
5. track teacher progress based on mentoring goals.	4.08	HE	5
Overall Grand Mean	3.93	HE	

Legend: **HE**- High Extent of Technical Assistance Practices

Table 2 presents the level of Master Teachers' technical assistance practices as perceived by both mentors and mentees, with an overall grand mean of 3.93, interpreted as a high extent. This indicates that instructional support is consistently implemented and contributes to continuous teacher development. The finding reflects the principles of Instructional Leadership Theory, which emphasizes mentoring, supervision, and sustained instructional support.

In mentoring and coaching (M = 3.98), the highest-rated practices were providing feedback after classroom observations (M = 4.09), assisting teachers in setting instructional goals (M = 4.02), and delivering coaching based on observed practices (M = 4.00). These results suggest that mentoring is grounded in reflective and classroom-based processes. However, lower ratings in the use of structured coaching models (M = 3.95) and one-on-one mentoring (M = 3.83) indicate that mentoring is not yet fully systematized.

For classroom observation and feedback (M = 4.20), Master Teachers demonstrated strong adherence to standards-based practices. The highest ratings in focusing on observable teaching behaviors (M = 4.29) and conducting pre-observation

conferences (M = 4.27) indicate that supervision is reflective and aligned with RPMS and PPST standards. However, slightly lower ratings in documentation (M = 4.12) and timely feedback (M = 4.11) suggest gaps in feedback processes.

In the facilitation of Learning Action Cells (LACs) (M = 4.20), practices such as documenting outputs and aligning topics with school goals (M = 4.03) indicate compliance with institutional requirements. However, lower ratings in peer collaboration (M = 4.00), facilitation (M = 3.97), and needs-based planning (M = 3.93) suggest that LACs remain more procedural than collaborative.

For monitoring and evaluation (M = 4.20), Master Teachers showed strong implementation of standards-based practices, particularly in using RPMS tools (M = 4.29) and coordinating with school heads (M = 4.26). Developmental practices such as supporting reflection (M = 4.21) and assisting in IPCRF completion (M = 4.16) indicate that evaluation is both accountability-driven and growth-oriented. However, lower ratings in tracking progress based on mentoring goals (M = 4.08) highlight the need for stronger follow-through mechanisms.

Overall, Master Teachers demonstrated a high extent of technical assistance practices across all domains, indicating strong instructional leadership. However, the findings highlight the need to strengthen mentoring structures, improve feedback and documentation processes, and enhance collaboration in LACs. These results are supported by Pitpit (2020) and Bush et al. (2018), who emphasized that structured mentoring and continuous professional development are essential in sustaining effective instructional leadership and improving teacher performance.

Table 3
LEVEL OF MASTER TEACHERS' WELL- BEING
n=163

1. Physical Well- being As a Master Teacher, I...	Mean	INT	RANK
1. have enough energy to fulfill my responsibilities as a Master Teacher	4.30	E	1.5
2. feel physically fit to sustain mentoring, coaching, and school activities	4.30	E	1.5
3. can balance my professional duties with my physical health needs	4.25	E	3
4. maintain healthy routines, such as rest, exercise, and a balanced diet	4.23	E	4.5
5. manage stress in ways that protect my physical well-being	4.23	E	4.5
Composite Mean	4.26	Excellent	
2. Emotional Well- being As a Master Teacher, I...	4.35	Excellent	
1. remain resilient when facing challenges in teaching and leadership	4.37	E	1.5
2. experience positive emotions that motivate me in my role	4.37	E	1.5
3. feel confident and encouraged in supporting other teachers	4.36	E	3.5

1. Physical Well- being As a Master Teacher, I...	Mean	INT	RANK
4.sustain optimism and hopefulness in my professional tasks	4.36	E	3.5
5.maintain emotional stability when handling conflicts or pressures	4.31	E	5
3. Social Well- being As a Master Teacher, I...	4.50	O	
1.encourage teamwork and shared responsibility in achieving school goals	4.53	O	1
2.maintain respectful and supportive interactions with stakeholders	4.52	O	2
3. feel connected and trusted within the school community	4.49	E	3
4. foster collegial relationships with fellow teachers	4.48	E	4
5. actively promote collaboration through Learning Action Cells (LACs) and peer learning	4.47	E	5
4. Professional Well- being As a Master Teacher, I...	4.36	Excellent	
1.remain committed to DepEd standards and school improvement initiatives	4.47	E	1
2.actively participate in professional development and training opportunities	4.43	E	2
3.demonstrate competence in mentoring and coaching teachers	4.34	E	3
4.feel satisfied in fulfilling my professional duties as a Master Teacher	4.33	E	4
5. balance workload demands with my own professional growth	4.27	E	5
Overall Grand Mean	4.37	Excellent	

Legend: **O**- Outstanding- teachers consistently sustain well- being at highest level
E- Excellent- teachers regularly sustain well-being

Table 3 presents the level of Master Teachers' well-being across four dimensions: physical, emotional, social, and professional, with an overall grand mean of 4.37, interpreted as excellent. This indicates that Master Teachers generally sustain a high level of well-being, which supports their instructional leadership and mentoring functions.

In terms of physical well-being (M = 4.26), Master Teachers demonstrated an excellent level, particularly in maintaining energy (M = 4.30) and physical fitness (M = 4.30) to perform their roles. However, slightly lower ratings in stress management (M = 4.23) suggest that sustained demands may occasionally affect consistency. This implies that physical well-being serves as a foundational resource for leadership effectiveness.

For emotional well-being (M = 4.35), results indicate a consistently high level of resilience, positive emotions, and confidence. The highest ratings in resilience (M = 4.37) and motivation (M = 4.37) reflect strong emotional stability. These findings suggest that Master Teachers possess affective resources that sustain motivation and adaptability.

Social well-being emerged as the strongest domain (M = 4.50, Outstanding), with high ratings in teamwork (M = 4.53) and stakeholder relationships (M = 4.52). This

indicates strong collegial interaction, trust, and collaboration within the school community. The findings highlight that professional relationships are central to instructional leadership.

In terms of professional well-being (M = 4.36), Master Teachers demonstrated strong commitment to standards (M = 4.47), active participation in professional development (M = 4.43), and competence in mentoring (M = 4.34). However, balancing workload with professional growth (M = 4.27) received the lowest rating, indicating that increasing demands may affect sustained development.

Overall, the findings indicate that Master Teachers are physically resilient, emotionally stable, socially connected, and professionally committed. However, the challenge of balancing workload and professional growth highlights the need for stronger institutional support. This is supported by Fajardo and Meimban (2025), who emphasized that teacher well-being is strongly influenced by workload conditions and access to professional development. Thus, sustaining instructional leadership requires not only individual resilience but also supportive organizational conditions.

Table 4
LEVEL OF CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY MASTER TEACHERS IN PROVIDING TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE
n=163

4.1 Time and Workload Constraints <i>As a Master Teacher, I...</i>	Mean	INT	RANK
1. have limited time to conduct mentoring due to teaching load	3.75	HE	1
2. teaching and administrative workload limit my ability to mentor effectively	3.72	HE	2
3. experience fatigue from overlapping responsibilities (e.g., teaching, mentoring, reporting)	3.59	HE	3
4. often have to postpone mentoring due to urgent school tasks	3.56	HE	4
5. struggle to balance technical assistance with other duties	3.50	HE	5
Composite Mean	3.63	HE	
4.2. Availability of Resources and Support <i>As a Master Teacher, I...</i>	3.27	ME	
1. need more administrative support for LACs and coaching	3.45	HE	1
1. have limited access to updated instructional materials and mentoring tools	3.35	ME	2
3. encounter technical difficulties (e.g., ICT access, connectivity)	3.33	ME	3
4. limited access to digital tools for feedback and monitoring	3.17	ME	4
5. do not receive timely updates or memos related to mentoring roles	3.03	ME	5
4.3. Clarity of Roles and Expectations <i>As a Master Teacher, I...</i>	2.76	ME	
1. observe inconsistency in how technical assistance responsibilities are assigned	2.82	ME	1

4.1 Time and Workload Constraints <i>As a Master Teacher, I...</i>	Mean	INT	RANK
2. receive limited guidance on how to structure mentoring and coaching	2.79	ME	2
3. rarely receive feedback on my technical assistance performance	2.77	ME	3
3. am unclear about my specific roles and expectations as a Master Teacher	2.76	ME	4
5. unsure how my mentoring duties align with RPMS indicators	2.67	ME	5
4.4. Capacity-Building or Training Opportunities <i>As a Master Teacher, I...</i>	3.40	ME	
1. need more opportunities to attend relevant seminars to enhance mentoring and coaching skills	3.71	HE	1
2. need support in using RPMS tools effectively	3.47	ME	2
3. rarely participate in division-led mentoring workshops	3.38	ME	3
4. lack access to online or modular training on technical assistance	3.24	ME	4
5. have not received adequate training on how to deliver technical assistance	3.18	ME	5
Overall Grand Mean	3.26	ME	

Legend: **HE**- High Extent of Challenges Experienced

ME- Moderate Extent of Challenges Experienced

Table 4 presents the level of challenges encountered by Master Teachers in providing technical assistance, with an overall grand mean of 3.26, interpreted as moderate. This indicates that while Master Teachers are able to perform their instructional leadership roles, they experience notable constraints that may affect the effectiveness and sustainability of their mentoring practices.

In terms of time and workload constraints ($M = 3.63$), challenges were experienced to a high extent, making it the most significant concern. Limited time for mentoring due to teaching load ($M = 3.75$) and the impact of combined teaching and administrative responsibilities ($M = 3.72$) were the highest-rated issues. Other concerns included fatigue from overlapping roles ($M = 3.59$) and difficulty balancing multiple responsibilities ($M = 3.50$). These findings indicate that instructional leadership is often constrained by competing demands.

For availability of resources and support ($M = 3.27$), challenges were experienced to a moderate extent. The need for more administrative support ($M = 3.45$), limited access to instructional materials ($M = 3.35$), and technical difficulties such as ICT and connectivity issues ($M = 3.33$) were the most common concerns. Lower ratings in communication and access to digital tools suggest gaps in institutional support systems.

In terms of clarity of roles and expectations ($M = 2.76$), challenges were also moderate but remain critical. Inconsistencies in role assignment ($M = 2.82$), limited guidance in mentoring ($M = 2.79$), and unclear expectations ($M = 2.76$) indicate systemic role ambiguity. These results suggest a gap between policy and actual implementation.

For capacity-building and training opportunities (M = 3.40), challenges were likewise moderate. The need for more relevant seminars (M = 3.71) and support in using RPMS tools (M = 3.47) were the most prominent concerns, while limited access to training and workshops indicates gaps in professional development.

Overall, the findings indicate that although Master Teachers remain committed to their roles, their effectiveness is constrained by workload pressures, limited resources, unclear role expectations, and insufficient training opportunities. These results are supported by Collie (2021) and Tarraya (2024), who emphasized that excessive workload and inadequate support systems significantly affect teachers' performance and instructional effectiveness. Addressing these challenges through improved workload management, adequate resource provision, clearer role definition, and continuous professional development is essential to strengthen instructional leadership and sustain technical assistance practices.

Table 5
LEVEL OF MASTER TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE
(Based on IPCRF SY 2024- 2025)
n= 163

Scale	Description	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding	13	7.97	2
3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory	150	92.02	1
2.500 – 3.499	Satisfactory	0	0	
1.500 – 2.499	Unsatisfactory	0	0	
Below 1.499	Poor	0	0	
Performance		Mean	INTERPRETATION	
Overall IPCRF Rating		4.41	Very Satisfactory	

Table 5 presents the performance of Master Teachers based on their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings for School Year 2024–2025. The overall mean score of 4.41, interpreted as Very Satisfactory, indicates that Master Teachers consistently demonstrate above-average performance in carrying out their instructional leadership roles.

The distribution shows that the majority of respondents (92.02%) fall within the Very Satisfactory category, while only 7.97% achieved an Outstanding rating. Notably, no respondents were rated Satisfactory, Unsatisfactory, or Poor. This pattern reflects a high level of competence and consistency in delivering mentoring, coaching, and technical assistance aligned with institutional standards. These findings suggest strong adherence to the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), indicating that Master Teachers effectively meet expected performance standards. However, the limited proportion of Outstanding ratings implies that while performance is commendable, there remains room for further enhancement toward higher levels of excellence.

Overall, the results confirm that Master Teachers demonstrate strong instructional leadership capacity. This finding is supported by Anub (2020), who emphasized that effective instructional leadership and mentoring competencies significantly contribute to improved school performance, and by Naguit (2024), who found that sustained supervision and coaching practices enhance teachers' performance and instructional quality. Strengthening professional development and institutional support may further elevate performance toward the Outstanding level.

Table 6
SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE AND MASTER TEACHERS' TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE PRACTICES, WELL-BEING, CHALLENGES, AND PERFORMANCE

Relationship	Test Statistic	p-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age and technical assistance practices	X ² =6.28	0.901	Fail to Reject H ₀	No significant relationship
Age and well-being	X ² =11.7	0.468		
Age and challenges encountered	X ² =16.1	0.587		
Age and performance	X ² =4.65	0.589		
Gender and technical assistance practices	X ² =0.185	0.192		
Gender and well-being	X ² =0.489	0.783		
Gender and challenges	X ² =2.37	0.499		
Gender and performance	X ² =7.54	0.006	Reject H ₀	Significant relationship
Length of service and technical assistance practices	X ² =7.44	0.683	Fail to Reject H ₀	No significant relationship
Length of service and well-being	X ² =12.6	0.245		
Length of service and challenges encountered	X ² =6.75	0.964		
Length of service and performance	X ² =3.10	0.685		
Number of teachers mentored and technical assistance practices	X ² =10.5	0.230		
Number of teachers mentored and well-being	X ² =1.88	0.984		
Number of teachers mentored and challenges encountered	X ² =18.2	0.109		
Number of teachers mentored and performance	X ² =7.68	0.466		
Educational attainment and technical assistance	X ² =8.05	0.234		
Educational attainment and well-being	X ² =1.44	0.963		
Educational attainment and challenges	X ² =12.8	0.171		
Educational attainment and performance	X ² =2.29	0.515		
Ancillary tasks and technical assistance	X ² =33.8	0.089		
Ancillary tasks and well-being	X ² =26.2	0.342		
Ancillary tasks and challenges	X ² =43.1	0.194		
Ancillary tasks and performance	X ² =4.65	0.589		
Teaching load and technical assistance	X ² =21.3	0.379		
Teaching load and well-being	X ² =21.3	0.379		
Teaching load and challenges	X ² =36.8	0.182		
Teaching load and performance	X ² =22.0	0.015	Reject H ₀	Significant relationship
Training/seminars and technical assistance	X ² =13.1	0.361	Fail to Reject H ₀	No significant relationship
Training/seminars and well-being	X ² =9.41	0.667		
Training/seminars and challenges	X ² =24.5	0.138		
Training/ Seminars attended and Performance	X ² =24.5	0.073		

Table 6 presents the relationships between the demographic profile of Master Teachers and their technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges encountered, and performance. The results generally show that most demographic variables do not have statistically significant relationships with the identified domains ($p > 0.05$), leading

to the acceptance of the null hypothesis in these cases. This indicates that Master Teachers demonstrate consistent instructional leadership practices regardless of differences in age, gender, length of service, educational attainment, mentoring load, ancillary tasks, and training exposure.

Specifically, age, length of service, and educational attainment were not significantly related to technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges, and performance. These findings suggest that instructional effectiveness is not determined solely by experience or academic qualifications, but rather by continuous professional engagement and system-based practices. This supports Boeskens et al. (2020) and Day et al. (2020), who emphasized that teacher effectiveness is more strongly influenced by sustained professional learning and organizational alignment than by demographic characteristics alone.

Gender likewise showed no significant relationship with technical assistance practices, well-being, and challenges encountered, indicating that instructional leadership roles are performed equitably across male and female Master Teachers. However, gender demonstrated a significant relationship with performance ($\chi^2 = 7.54$, $p = 0.006$), suggesting that performance outcomes may be influenced by contextual or evaluative factors rather than differences in competence.

Similarly, the number of teachers mentored and ancillary tasks were not significantly related to any domain, indicating that variations in workload distribution do not necessarily reduce effectiveness. This implies that Master Teachers are able to maintain consistent performance through adaptive strategies and structured support systems.

A key finding is that teaching load has a significant relationship with performance ($\chi^2 = 22.0$, $p = 0.015$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. While teaching load does not significantly affect practices, well-being, or challenges, it directly influences performance outcomes. This suggests that although Master Teachers sustain their roles despite heavy workloads, the intensity of teaching responsibilities affects the quality of performance. This finding is supported by Collie (2021) and Kim and Asbury (2020), who found that excessive workload and job demands significantly impact teacher performance and instructional effectiveness.

Training and seminars attended were also not significantly related to any domain, indicating that participation alone does not guarantee improved outcomes. This suggests that the effectiveness of professional development depends on its quality, relevance, and practical application in teaching contexts.

Overall, the findings reveal that instructional leadership practices, well-being, and challenges are largely consistent across demographic groups, reflecting the influence of standardized professional systems. However, performance outcomes are shaped by contextual and organizational factors, particularly teaching load. These results support the view that teacher effectiveness is system-driven and context-dependent, as

emphasized by Boeskens et al. (2020) and Collie (2021). Thus, enhancing Master Teachers' performance requires not only maintaining professional standards but also strengthening organizational conditions, particularly workload management and support systems, to sustain effective instructional leadership.

Table 7
RELATIONSHIPS AMONG VARIABLES OF THE MASTER TEACHERS

Variables	Pearson's r	df	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
7.1. technical assistance practices & well-being	-0.009	161	0.912	Fail to reject H ₀₂	Not Significant
7.2. technical assistance practices & challenges encountered	0.064	161	0.419		
7.3. technical assistance practices & performance	-0.060	158	0.449		
7.4. challenges encountered & well-being	-0.116	161	0.142		
7.5. challenges encountered & performance	0.058	158	0.466		
7.6. well-being & performance	-0.003	158	0.966		

Note. *p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001

Table 7 presents the relationships among technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges encountered, and performance of Master Teachers. The results reveal that all examined relationships are statistically non-significant ($p > 0.05$), with negligible Pearson's r coefficients across all variable pairings. For instance, technical assistance and well-being ($r = -0.009$, $p = 0.912$) and well-being and performance ($r = -0.003$, $p = 0.966$) both indicate no meaningful association. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) is not rejected, confirming the absence of significant linear relationships among the variables.

These findings suggest that technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges, and performance operate as largely independent constructs within the context of Master Teachers' professional practice. The near-zero correlations imply that the provision of instructional support does not automatically translate into improved well-being or enhanced performance, and that experienced challenges do not directly influence performance outcomes.

This result can be explained through the Job Demands–Resources (JD–R) Model, which posits that job resources such as mentoring and coaching primarily support task-related outcomes, while well-being is more strongly shaped by job demands such as workload and organizational pressures (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Similarly, Mercer et al. (2016) emphasized that teacher well-being is influenced more by contextual and emotional conditions than by instructional support alone.

Moreover, the absence of significant relationships may be attributed to the standardized nature of performance evaluation systems. The Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) tends to produce relatively uniform performance ratings, which may limit variability and reduce the likelihood of detecting statistical relationships among variables.

Overall, the findings indicate that technical assistance, well-being, challenges, and performance are influenced by distinct factors rather than direct interactions. This highlights the need for a dual-focused approach in educational management: strengthening instructional support systems to enhance teaching effectiveness, while simultaneously addressing workload conditions and well-being to ensure sustainable and holistic professional development among Master Teachers.

DISCUSSION

This study focused on examining the technical assistance practices, well-being, challenges, and performance of Master Teachers in public secondary schools in the Division of Bohol for School Year 2025–2026. It aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of how Master Teachers carry out their instructional leadership roles within the context of mentoring, coaching, supervision, and teacher support. Specifically, the study described the demographic profile of Master Teachers and assessed the extent of their technical assistance practices, their level of well-being, and the challenges they encountered in delivering instructional support. It also evaluated their performance based on IPCRF ratings and examined the relationships among these variables. The overall goal was to generate insights that would inform the development of a Professional Development Program to strengthen instructional leadership and support systems for Master Teachers.

Findings

Presented below are the specific findings of the study, organized according to the sequence of the stated sub-problems. The results highlight the profile of Master Teachers, the extent of their technical assistance practices, their level of well-being, the challenges they encountered, their performance, and the relationships among these variables.

1. Profile of Master Teachers

1.1 Age of Respondents. The majority were middle-aged (45–49 years), about 29.4 %. This age bracket reflects maturity and readiness for leadership responsibilities, consistent with literature linking age and experience to stronger instructional judgment.

1.2 Gender of Respondents. Predominantly female (86.5%), mirroring the national composition of the teaching workforce. This confirms that gender distribution in Bohol aligns with national trends, though mentoring effectiveness was not significantly influenced by gender.

1.3 Educational Attainment. A considerable proportion held postgraduate degrees (master's or doctoral units), strengthening competence and credibility. This justifies their ability to apply research-based strategies and provide higher-level instructional guidance.

1.4 Ancillary Tasks/ designations. A considerable number performed multiple roles (committees, coordination, admin duties). This extended responsibility justifies the finding that workload indicators limit sustained mentoring.

1.5 Length of Service as Master Teacher. Most had less than five years in the position, suggesting many are still transitioning into leadership roles. This justifies the need for structured mentoring frameworks to support novice Master Teachers.

1.6 Number of Teachers Mentored/Supervised. Loads varied; larger groups required structured approaches, while smaller groups allowed individualized mentoring. This justifies the importance of balancing mentoring load to avoid emotional strain.

1.7 Teaching load. High teaching loads limited time for mentoring, confirming that instructional performance is sensitive to teaching load intensity.

1.8 Trainings/Seminars Attended. Participation was uneven; some had strong exposure to professional development, while others had limited opportunities.

2. Technical Assistance Practices

2.1 Mentoring and Coaching. Practiced to a high extent but often informal. This justifies the need for structured frameworks to ensure consistency and sustainability.

2.2 Classroom Observation and Feedback. Strongest practice with composite mean of 4.20, aligned with PPST and RPMS standards. This justifies the conclusion that Master Teachers are fulfilling their mandated supervisory role effectively.

2.3 Facilitation of LACs and Peer Learning. Consistently implemented, promoting collaborative growth. This justifies the role of LACs as institutionalized platforms for professional learning.

2.4 Monitoring and Evaluation of Teacher Performance. Regularly conducted, ensuring accountability. This justifies the link between technical assistance and measurable IPCRF outcomes.

3. Well-Being of Master Teachers

3.1 Physical Well-Being. Rated high, though prolonged workload posed risks of strain. This justifies the need for workload management to sustain energy for mentoring.

3.2 Emotional Well-Being. High resilience supported confidence and mentoring effectiveness. This justifies the conclusion that emotional stability strengthens instructional leadership.

3.3 Social Well-Being. Strongest domain, sustained by collegial relationships. This justifies the importance of collaborative cultures in reducing burnout.

3.4 Professional Well-Being. High but vulnerable due to workload and role ambiguity. This justifies the recommendation to clarify roles and strengthen recognition systems.

4. Challenges Encountered

4.1 Time and Workload Constraints. Rated high with composite mean of 3.63, the most pressing issue. This justifies the conclusion that workload pressures compromise mentoring depth.

4.2 Availability of Resources and Support. Moderate, with gaps in materials and institutional backing. This justifies the recommendation for systemic reinforcement of instructional support.

4.3 Clarity of Roles and Expectations. Moderate, with ambiguity contributing to stress. This justifies the call for clearer role definitions to stabilize leadership.

4.4 Capacity-Building or Training Opportunities. Moderate, with uneven access limiting adaptation to reforms. This justifies the need for structured professional development programs.

5. Performance

IPCRF ratings averaged 4.41 (Very Satisfactory), close to Outstanding. This justifies the conclusion that Master Teachers are meeting standards effectively despite constraints, but sustaining excellence requires addressing workload and role clarity.

6. Relationship Between Profile and Variables

Age, length of service, ancillary roles, training, mentoring load, workload, and educational attainment significantly influenced outcomes. This justifies the conclusion that demographic and professional attributes shape instructional leadership effectiveness. Gender showed no significant effect, justifying that mentoring capacity is not determined by gender differences.

7. Relationship Among Variables

No significant interrelationships were found among technical assistance, well-being, challenges, and performance. This justifies the conclusion that these domains operate independently and must be addressed separately in interventions.

8. Proposed Program

A Professional Development Program was designed to strengthen mentoring practices, clarify roles, manage workload, and support well-being. This justifies the study's contribution to policy and practice, ensuring sustained instructional leadership effectiveness in Bohol.

Conclusions

The study concludes that Master Teachers in the Division of Bohol are highly competent in technical assistance and demonstrate strong well-being and performance. However, their capacity to sustain instructional leadership is undermined by workload intensification, fragmented training, and role ambiguity. Effectiveness is shaped less by personal demographics and more by institutional and organizational conditions, with workload distribution, role clarity, and professional development emerging as decisive factors. The consistently high performance of Master Teachers reflects resilient professionalism that endures despite time and workload pressures, suggesting both a commendable dedication level and a potential risk of burnout. It underscores the urgent need for structured support systems, equitable workload policies, and strengthened professional development to sustain their leadership impact.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and suggestions made by the respondents, the following recommendations can be made:

- 1. Reduce Workload.** The Department of Education may strengthen its policy on deloading Master Teachers from excessive teaching and ancillary tasks to have ample time to perform their real functions.
- 2. Role Clarification.** The Department of Education may define clearly the structured roles for Master Teachers to minimize role ambiguity and ensure their primary function remains instructional support rather than administrative overload.
- 3. Capacity Building and Needs-Based Training.** The Department of Education and the Division of Bohol may formalize and embed structured yearly professional development into existing systems, focusing on coaching, mentoring strategies, and data-driven feedback.
- 4. Shift TA from Compliance to Collaboration.** School heads and administrators may redesign technical assistance to emphasize supportive mentoring through structured pre- and post-observation conferences, reflective questioning, demonstration teaching, and growth-oriented feedback cycles that foster trust, collaboration, and continuous improvement.
- 5. Strengthen Professional Learning Communities (LACs).** School heads may enhance LAC sessions through targeted workshops and structured, inquiry-based

discussions led by Master Teachers. These sessions should promote reflective practice and collaborative growth aligned with teachers' developmental needs.

6. **Adopt Data-Driven Coaching Models.** Master Teachers may align technical assistance with actual classroom needs by using student performance data, teacher self-assessments, and observation results, ensuring support is targeted, practical, and measurable.
7. **Support Master Teachers' Well-Being.** The Department of Education and DepEd Bohol may integrate a unified wellness program to sustain the physical, emotional, and professional well-being of Master Teachers. This initiative may also extend to all DepEd teachers and personnel to strengthen resilience, effectiveness, and long-term instructional leadership.
8. **Advance Research on Instructional Leadership.** Future researchers may deepen investigations on technical assistance strategies and coping mechanisms through qualitative inquiries, generating richer insights to strengthen mentoring and instructional leadership practices.

PROPOSED PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM SUSTAINING INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP AND WELL- BEING OF MASTER TEACHERS IN THE DIVISION OF BOHOL

Rationale

The study revealed that Master Teachers in the division of Bohol consistently demonstrate high levels of technical assistance and performance, yet face systemic challenges such as workload intensification, fragmented training, and role ambiguity. While their IPCRF ratings are Very Satisfactory, professional well-being is compromised by multiple ancillary roles and uneven access to training. This program is designed to sustain instructional leadership capacity while safeguarding well-being, ensuring that Master Teachers remain effective, resilient, and prepared for long-term leadership continuity. Notably, technical assistance will be reframed as collaborative mentoring integrated with values education, fostering trust, reflective practice, and character-driven leadership.

I. General Objective

To sustain and strengthen the instructional leadership and well-being of Master Teachers in Bohol division through structured, collaborative, and evidence-based professional development.

Specific Objectives

The program aims to:

1. Institutionalize collaborative mentoring and coaching frameworks for consistency and sustainability.

2. Rationalize workload and clarify roles to reduce stress and role ambiguity.
3. Strengthen access to updated instructional materials, ICT tools, and administrative support.
4. Expand training opportunities in mentoring, supervision, RPMS/PPST, and leadership development.
5. Promote resilience and professional well-being through psychosocial and stress-management programs.
6. Ensure succession planning by preparing younger teachers for future leadership roles.

II. Program Components

Program Area	Component	Desired Outcome
Mentoring & Coaching	Collaborative coaching frameworks with values integration	Consistent, sustainable mentoring practices aligned with RPMS/PPST standards.
Workload & Role Management	Rationalization of assignments	Reduced stress, clearer expectations, and balanced distribution of duties.
Resource & ICT Support	Provision of updated tools	Improved technical assistance effectiveness and instructional supervision.
Capacity-Building	Targeted training modules	Enhanced competence in mentoring, supervision, and leadership.
Well-being & Resilience	Stress management and support	Stronger resilience, reduced burnout, and sustained professional well-being.
Succession Planning	Leadership continuity initiatives	Prepared younger teachers for future leadership roles, ensuring stability.

III. Program Matrix

Program Title	Objectives	Activities	Persons Involved	Timeline	Success Indicators
Mentoring Excellence	Institutionalize structured coaching	Training on GROW, CLEAR models; peer mentoring workshops	Master Teachers, School Heads, DepEd Trainers	SY 2026–2027	Increased consistency in mentoring practices; improved mentee feedback
Workload Balance	Rationalize ancillary roles	Policy workshops; workload audits;	DepEd Division Office, School	SY 2026–2027	Reduced reports of role ambiguity;

Program Title	Objectives	Activities	Persons Involved	Timeline	Success Indicators
		role clarification sessions	Heads, Master Teachers		improved professional well-being scores
Resource Access	Strengthen ICT and materials support	Provision of updated instructional materials; ICT integration training	DepEd Division Office, ICT Coordinators	SY 2026–2027	Increased use of ICT tools; improved technical assistance ratings
Leadership Development	Expand training opportunities	RPMS/PPST seminars; instructional supervision workshops	Master Teachers, DepEd Trainers	SY 2026–2027	Higher IPCRF ratings; improved confidence in leadership roles
Resilience Program	Promote psychosocial support	Stress management seminars; mental health interventions	Master Teachers, Guidance Counselors	SY 2026–2027	Reduced burnout indicators; sustained high well-being ratings
Succession Planning	Ensure leadership continuity	Mentoring younger teachers; leadership shadowing programs	Master Teachers, Junior Teachers, School Heads	SY 2026–2027	Increased readiness of younger teachers; continuity in leadership roles

Mechanics of Implementation

- 1. Program Launch:** Orientation with Master Teachers and school heads to align objectives and expectations.
- 2. Capacity-Building Sessions:** Conducted quarterly, focusing on mentoring, supervision, RPMS/PPST, and leadership.
- 3. Resource Provision:** Division office to allocate updated instructional materials and ICT tools.
- 4. Monitoring and Evaluation:** Regular assessment through IPCRF ratings, well-being surveys, and workload audits.
- 5. Feedback Mechanisms:** Continuous feedback from mentees, school heads, and Master Teachers to refine program delivery.
- 6. Sustainability Measures:** Integration of program components into DepEd's annual training and leadership development agenda.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study followed established ethical standards for quantitative research. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents.

Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured, with no personal information disclosed. All data were securely stored and used only for academic purposes in compliance with the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173). Participants could withdraw or skip questions at any time. No incentives were given, and no conflict of interest was declared.

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